

Effect of Google Sites-assisted Flipped Classroom Discovery Learning Model and Cognitive Style on Mathematics Problem-Solving Skills and Student Learning Independence

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Abstract

Background: Mathematics problem-solving skills and student learning independence are essential for facing 21st-century challenges. Conventional teacher-centered approaches limit student collaboration and independent exploration.

Objectives : This study investigates how the Google Sites-assisted Discovery Flipped Classroom (DFC) model affects students' mathematics problem-solving skills and learning independence while analysing the influence of cognitive styles on learning outcomes and exploring potential interactions between these variables.

Methodology : In the study, a quasi-experimental design was employed with SMA Negeri 4 Halmahera Timur's students enlisted in the 120 11-grade students` 2x2 factorial pattern. The

participants were further divided into a control group that used the Direct Instruction method and an experimental group that employed the DFC model. The data were gained through pretests and post-tests conducted on students to measure their problem-solving skills and learning independence. Then, the values were used to analyse the interaction between the variables using the MANOVA test with the use of SPSS 27.

Results : The outcomes indicated that applying the DFC model, which Google Sites support, can significantly enhance students' problem-solving and learning independence. MANOVA analysis verified that the DFC model was the main factor on both terms, and field-independent students were the best performers. It also appeared that the cognitive style had a significant effect on interaction, especially in the field-dependent cognitive style of the students.

Conclusion: This research has confirmed that the learning model DFC, which Google Sites facilitates, can effectively develop students' mathematics problem-solving skills and individual learning. The student's cognitive style is another factor essential to the learning outcome, whereas field-independent students show excellent performance. Using the DFC model in conjunction with cognitive style would show that this model would be conducive to the field-dependent students becoming independent in their learning.

Unique Contribution: This research is unique in its focus on developing technology in mathematics education through the DFC model, which leads to students' mastery of academic skills and respects the differences in cognitive styles. This research is novel in that it explores how adaptive learning models a digital-age student's unique needs.

Recommendations : According to the research results, implementation of the DFC model in the learning process, particularly in the mathematics area, should be seen as a viable option for teachers and educators concerned with that matter. Moreover, it is vital to consider differences in students' cognitive styles when designing more inclusive and adaptive learning strategies.

Key words : Discovery Flipped Classroom, Google Sites, Problem-Solving Skills, Learning Independence, Cognitive Style, Mathematics Education.

Introduction

Problem-solving in mathematics and autonomy in learning are two important aspects that dictate whether students are ready to face the challenges of the 21st century. All over the world, mathematics is seen as a tool for calculation and a basis for logical, analytical, and creative thinking (Stacey, 2011). However, many students still fail to use mathematical concepts in everyday situations (*PISA 2018 Results (Volume I)*, 2019). This incapacity affects students' grades and self-assurance in tackling challenging problems beyond school. On the other hand, acquiring self-mastery - the ability to manage, regulate, and assess one's own learning - is often overlooked in a school system that is generally highly autocratic (Zimmerman, 2002). Learning independence is fundamental to enable learners to be lifelong learners in today's dynamic digital world.

Most schools use traditional teaching methods that focus heavily on instructors explaining things to students. This approach to teaching does not enable students to explore concepts independently, collaborate, or find solutions to challenges (Freeman et al., 2014). Because of this, most students are passive, over-depend on the instructor's message, and struggle to transfer what they learn to everyday life. As technology continues to evolve at a breakneck pace, the disparity between conventional ways of learning and the needs of the present times is becoming

increasingly apparent. Students from Generation Alpha and Z, having grown up with technology, need more interactive, flexible, and tailored-to-their-learning-style approaches to learning (Hrastinski, 2019).

The Discovery Flipped Classroom (DFC) method is a novel idea that combines two effective methods: flipped classroom and discovery learning. In the flipped classroom, students learn essential content at home on their own using online resources, and classroom time is spent on discussion, experiments, and problem-solving (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2018). At the same time, discovery learning focuses on searching for concepts through exploratory activity with the teacher acting as a facilitator (Bruner, 1961). Blending these two models should create a learning environment that allows students to think logically, work independently, and reflect deeply. The model will only work, however, with the proper technology support. Tools like Google Sites are also of particular relevance. Google Sites is a simple and free tool that enables teachers to create interactive learning content (e.g., videos, quizzes, and simulations) for students to learn at their own pace. It also includes a section where the students can collaborate (Al-Marroof & Al-Emran, 2018).

Another dimension often neglected is the difference in students' thinking, specifically between field-independent and field-dependent learning styles. Field-independent learners are more likely to structure information and can do so autonomously, while field-dependent learners depend on outside help and instructors more (Tinajero & Páramo, 1998). These differences can modify students' reactions to technology-based learning models like DFC. For example, field-independent students can learn independently using Google Sites effectively, while field-dependent students require more specific instructions (Chen & Macredie, 2002). Earlier research on the DFC model does not tend to examine in detail how cognitive style affects the success of the learning model (Lo & Hew, 2017). Such knowledge enables learning to be tailored fairly and equitably for everyone.

Research Objectives

This research comes to fill the gap by investigating three main aspects: (1) the extent of the influence of DFC model assisted by Google Sites on mathematics problem-solving skills and student learning independence, (2) the extent of the influence of cognitive style on mathematics problem-solving skills and student learning independence, and (3) how the interaction of DFC model assisted by Google Sites and Google Sites on mathematics problem-solving skills and student learning independence. The findings are expected to enrich the repertoire of educational theories and provide practical guidance for teachers in integrating technology with student-centered pedagogical approaches. In a policy context, this research encourages digital transformation in the education sector by utilizing affordable resources, such as Google Sites, to be widely adopted even in schools with limited infrastructure. As such, these efforts align with the vision of global education that emphasizes equitable access, improved learning quality, and the development of 21st-century competencies.

Literature Review

Google Sites-assisted Flipped Classroom Discovery Model

Discovery Flipped Classroom (DFC) combines discovery learning and flipped classrooms. DFC reverses the conventional pattern of learning by moving passive learning (e.g., lecturing) outside the classroom and reserving class time for debating, experimenting, and problem-solving (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2018). This model's strong points lie in promoting student-student and student-teacher interaction and flexibility in content availability Lo & Hew, (2017). Discovery learning focuses more on discovering concepts through firsthand experience, where the students construct knowledge through direct encounters (Bruner, 1961). A blend of these two models guarantees a learning environment that promotes active, critical, and independent learners.

The use of Google Sites as a DFC support platform provides significant advantages. Google Sites facilitates the presentation of interactive materials such as videos, simulations, and quizzes, that can be accessed at any time, and enables collaboration between students through commenting and document-sharing features (Al-Marouf & Al-Emran, 2018). Research by Hrastinski, (2019) shows that web-based platforms such as Google Sites increase student engagement and learning independence, especially in distance learning. However, their effectiveness depends on designing structured materials that are adaptive to students' needs (Chen & Macredie, 2002).

Cognitive Styles (Field-Independent and Field-Dependent)

Cognitive style relates to how we process information and respond to the environment in which we are learning. Field-independent (FI) learners are likelier to differentiate between information and context, work autonomously, and employ internal analysis (Tinajero & Páramo, 1998). Field dependence (FD) learners rely more heavily on outside schemata (e.g., teacher rules or scaffolding of an agenda; Witkin et al., 1977). It guides learners towards types of learning, as this distinction is crucial. FI students are used to technology-based self-instructional approaches, but FD students require concise guidance and scaffolding (Chen & Macredie, 2002).

Lo and Hew, (2017) found that cognitive style can serve as a significant moderator when it comes to the effect of the flipped classroom model. FI students improved quickly because they could manage time and discover material independently. On the contrary, without any structured guidelines and directions, FD students struggle, and as a result, they need extra support through video tutorials, one by one, or instructional forums.

Maths Problem-solving Skills (Based on Polya's Stages)

Polya, (1945) defines mathematical problem-solving skills as the students' application of mathematical concepts in real-life situations by using four stages: (1) understanding the problem, (2) planning the solution, (3) implementing the plan, and (4) evaluating the result. According to the *(PISA 2018 Results (Volume I), 2019)* report, proficient in problem-solving students have high levels of metacognition, which involves monitoring the general thinking process and updating strategies when necessary.

This is where the Google Sites-assisted DFC model comes in; this can further build these skills by presenting more complex contextualized problems and giving students room for independent inquiry. For instance, students can study cases through case videos on Google Sites and then discuss the solution in class (Stacey, 2011). However, its effectiveness can vary with the complexity of the problem and the match to students' cognitive level (Freeman et al., 2014).

Learning Independence

Learning independence is defined as the ability of students to organize, monitor, and evaluate their learning process by themselves (Zimmerman, 2002). That includes goal setting, time management, and self-reflection. According to research by (Al-Marouf & Al-Emran, 2018), students can access digital platforms like Google Sites at their own pace, providing them with learning independence. However, this independence is not given automatically - it demands a learning design that fosters student responsibility and initiative (Hrastinski, 2019).

FI students are usually more independent in their learning because they work independently more frequently and organize strategies for their learning (Tinajero & Páramo, 1998). FD students, for example, are less likely to be intrinsically motivated and rely on extrinsic motivation, which includes differentiation of scaffolding based on students' cognitive styles should be considered when implementing DFC.

Research Objectives

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Research Hypothesis

The Null Hypothesis of Research:

- Hypothesis 1 : There is no effect of the discovery of the flipped classroom learning model assisted by Google sites on students' mathematical problem-solving skills.
- Hypothesis 2 : There is no effect of the discovery of the flipped classroom learning model assisted by Google sites on students' learning.
- Hypothesis 3 : There is no effect of cognitive style on students' mathematical problem-solving skills.

Hypothesis 4 : There is no effect of cognitive style on students' independence.

Hypothesis 5 : There is no interaction between the discovery of the flipped classroom model assisted by Google Sites and cognitive style on students' mathematical problem-solving skills.

Hypothesis 6 : There is no interaction between the discovery of the flipped classroom model assisted by Google sites and cognitive style on student learning independence.

Research Methods

Research Design

This research employed a quasi-experimental design by using a 2x2 factorial pattern to investigate the impact of the Discovery Flipped Classroom (DFC) model aided by Google Sites (independent variable) on mathematics problem-solving abilities as well as learning self-reliance (dependent variable), with cognitive style (field-dependent/field-independent) as a moderator variable. The experimental group used the DFC model, and the control group used Direct Instruction learning. For analysing data, a Pretest and post-test for students' abilities were followed to calculate the differences and changes, while the MANOVA test was used for the interaction between variables with the help of SPSS 27.

Intervention Details

The intervention involved implementing the Discovery Flipped Classroom (DFC) model, which integrates Google Sites to deliver instructional content on a concept or problem-solving strategy. Each episode was allocated 90 minutes in the classroom, during which students engaged in problem-solving activities and discussions related to the concepts they studied online. Students were encouraged to engage in independent learning at home through Google Sites without any time restrictions, allowing them to explore the material at their own pace. Fidelity of the intervention was ensured through regular observations and feedback sessions with trained mathematics teachers from SMA Negeri 4 Halmahera Timur, who facilitated the intervention and received professional development on the DFC model and the use of Google Sites prior to the study. This structured approach ensured that the DFC model was implemented consistently and effectively throughout the intervention.

Participants

The subjects of this research were 120 students of the eleventh grade of SMA Negeri 4 Halmahera Timur in the 2024/2025 academic year, which divided into four classes (XI-A and XI-B as the experimental group and XI-C and XI-D as the control group). Two-stage cluster sampling, where first-stage units are defined as plants and second-stage units are defined as classes. The Group Embedded Figures Test (GEFT) was used to group students by cognitive style (field-independent/field-dependent) to guarantee that both groups were represented in the factorial design.

Research Instruments

The research instruments included: (1) a GEFT test to classify students' cognitive style, (2) a description test of mathematical problem-solving skills based on Polya's indicators (expert validation and Alpha Cronbach reliability test >0.6), and (3) Likert scale learning r-count $> r$ -table ($\alpha=5\%$) and reliable if Alpha Cronbach >0.6 .

The validation process of the research instruments was conducted comprehensively to ensure the feasibility and reliability of the learning devices and measuring instruments. First, the validation of learning devices involved three components: (1) Educational Technology experts from Unesa validated lesson plans/teaching modules with an average score of 95%, where the language aspect achieved a perfect score (100%), while the content of the material obtained 92%; (2) Google Sites media obtained an average of 93%, with the highest content suitability (95%) and the lowest arrangement format (88%), which was then refined through simplifying the display; (3) Mathematics Education experts from UNM validated Mathematics Functions materials with an average of 97%, including language clarity (100%) and content relevance (95%). All three components were declared fit for use after minor revisions.

Second, the mathematics problem-solving skills test instrument was validated by UNM Mathematics Education experts, resulting in an average score of 95%, with the content aspect rated at 100%, the construction aspect at 90%, and the language aspect at 95%. Further statistical tests conducted on 30 students showed that both test items met the validity criteria, with r-count values greater than the r-table threshold of 0.361. Table 1 presents the validity test results for the mathematics problem-solving skills test items.

Table 1. Results of the Validity Test of Mathematics Problem-solving Skills Test Items

No.	r-Count	r-Table	Description
1	0,961	0,361	Valid
2	0,973	0,361	Valid

The reliability of the mathematics problem-solving skills test was also evaluated, producing a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.924 for the two items. This result confirms that the test instrument has very high internal consistency and is suitable for further use in measuring student performance. As shown in table 1, both test items for the mathematics problem-solving skills were validated and found to be reliable.

Third, the learning independence instrument went through three stages of validation: (1) expert validation resulted in an average score of 90% (content aspect: 95%, language, and presentation: 88%) with revision of 1 item removal; (2) empirical validity test on 30 students showed 27 out of 31 items were valid (4 invalid items were removed). Table 2 presents the validity test results for the learning independence instrument.

Table 2. Validity Test Results of Learning Independence Questionnaire Items

No.	r-Count	r-Table	Description
1	0,771	0,361	Valid
2	0,818	0,361	Valid
3	0,148	0,361	Invalid

4	0,407	0,361	Valid
5	0,815	0,361	Valid
6	0,734	0,361	Valid
7	0,842	0,361	Valid
8	0,580	0,361	Valid
9	0,557	0,361	Valid
10	0,676	0,361	Valid
11	0,592	0,361	Valid
12	0,761	0,361	Valid
13	0,719	0,361	Valid
14	0,518	0,361	Valid
15	0,470	0,361	Valid
16	0,418	0,361	Valid
17	0,855	0,361	Valid
18	0,354	0,361	Invalid
19	0,386	0,361	Valid
20	0,829	0,361	Valid
21	0,514	0,361	Valid
22	0,818	0,361	Valid
23	0,301	0,361	Invalid
24	0,699	0,361	Valid
25	0,540	0,361	Valid
26	0,570	0,361	Valid
27	0,774	0,361	Valid
28	0,189	0,361	Invalid
29	0,857	0,361	Valid
30	0,751	0,361	Valid
31	0,382	0,361	Valid

Cronbach's Alpha was used to evaluate the reliability of the learning independence instrument, and the 31 items returned a value of 0.942. This high value indicates exceptional internal consistency and demonstrates the instrument's dependability in measuring learning independence among students.

The conclusion shows that all instruments fulfill the criteria of content, construct, and reliability validity ($\alpha > 0.6$), making them suitable for accurate and measurable research data collection. This validation process ensures methodological credibility in evaluating the effectiveness of the learning model and related variables.

Data Analysis

This study used an independent t-test to verify the initial equality of groups and MANOVA to test the effect of the learning model, cognitive style, and their interaction with the help of IBM SPSS 27 ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Normality and Homogeneity Test

Normality (Kolmogorov-Smirnov) and homogeneity (Levene) tests² were conducted on the data from the pre-test and post-test of mathematical problem-solving skills and learning independence. The normality test showed that, on all variables, both group experimental and control, the experimental group and control pretest (problem-solving skills): $p = 0.090- 0.199$; (learning independence): $p = 0.093-0.171$) and the post-test (problem-solving skills): $p = 0.178-0.189$; (learning independence): $p = 0.088-0.186$) (table 2). The homogeneity test of data variance between the two groups also met the criteria ($p > 0.05$), with the highest Levene value of 0.854 (problem-solving skills) and 0.648-0.218 (learning independence), thus indicating homogeneous data variance. Because the assumptions of normality and homogeneity are satisfied, parametric statistical analysis can be validly conducted.

Group Equivalence Test

Statistical t-test analysis of mathematics problem-solving skills obtained a significance value of 0.551 ($p > 0.05$), which indicated that there was no significant difference between the experimental class (mean 31.7363) and the control class (mean 32.7083). The t-test on the results of learning average pretest of the experimental class was 66.2667, and the control class was 65.7333. Thus, both classes have comparable baseline abilities, and this method balances out the potential differences in performance, allowing future analyses to be valid.

Research Results

**Table 5. Description of Manova Test Data
Descriptive Statistics**

	Learning Model	Cognitive Style	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Maths Problem-solving Skills	Discovery Flipped Classroom with Google Sites	Field Independent	79.32	9.843	25
		Field Dependent	79.11	8.567	35
		Total	79.20	9.040	60
	Direct Instruction	Field Independent	65.96	7.036	27
		Field Dependent	53.73	6.578	33
		Total	59.23	9.108	60
	Total	Field Independent	72.38	10.782	52
		Field Dependent	66.79	14.876	68
		Total	69.22	13.496	120
Learning Independence	Discovery Flipped Classroom with Google Sites	Field Independent	104.8400	7.54255	25
		Field Dependent	99.1429	9.61660	35
		Total	101.5167	9.19007	60
	Direct Instruction	Field Independent	97.2963	5.23167	27
		Field Dependent	79.8182	6.90314	33
		Total	87.6833	10.71430	60
	Total	Field Independent	100.9231	7.43032	52

	Field Dependent	89.7647	12.82036	68
	Total	94.6000	12.12567	120

Descriptive analysis of post-test data described a significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the experimental group that applied the Discovery Flipped Classroom (DFC) model assisted by Google Sites compared to a control group that applied direct learning. The experimental group students obtained an average of 79.20 (SD = 9.040) (problem-solving skill in mathematics), while the control group only achieved 59.23 (SD = 9.108). According to the results in the case of learning independence, the average was better than their field-dependent (FD) peers on both problem-solving skills (72.38 vs. 66.79) and learning independence (100.92 vs. 89.76) when the same groups were compared based on cognitive styles. These data suggest a possible impact of the learning model and cognitive style on learning outcomes (Table 5).

**Table 6. Manova test analysis results
Tests of Between-Subjects Effects**

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	Maths Problem-solving Skills	14183.875 ^a	3	4727.958	73.199	.000	.654
	Learning Independence	10750.616 ^b	3	3583.539	61.619	.000	.614
Intercept	Maths Problem-solving Skills	569144.272	1	569144.272	8811.587	.000	.987
	Learning Independence	1068601.136	1	1068601.136	18374.495	.000	.994
Model_Learning	Maths Problem-solving Skills	11044.698	1	11044.698	170.996	.000	.596
	Learning Independence	5311.617	1	5311.617	91.333	.000	.441
Cognitive Style	Maths Problem-solving Skills	1138.892	1	1138.892	17.633	.000	.132
	Learning Independence	3951.782	1	3951.782	67.951	.000	.369
Learning Model * Cognitive Style	Maths Problem-solving Skills	1064.813	1	1064.813	16.486	.000	.124
	Learning Independence	1021.189	1	1021.189	17.559	.000	.131
Error	Maths Problem-solving Skills	7492.491	116	64.590			

	Learning Independence	6746.184	116	58.157			
Total	Maths Problem-solving Skills	596590.000	120				
	Learning Independence	1091396.000	120				
Corrected Total	Maths Problem-solving Skills	21676.367	119				
	Learning Independence	17496.800	119				

- a. R Squared = ,654 (Adjusted R Squared = ,645)
- b. R Squared = ,614 (Adjusted R Squared = ,604)

The results of the MANOVA test (Table 6) showed that the DFC model assisted with Google Sites had a significant effect on increasing mathematics problem-solving skills ($F = 170.996, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.596$) and learning independence ($F = 91.333, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.441$). Cognitive style was another important factor explaining the results where FI students performed better in both variables ($p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.132$ for skills; $p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.369$ for independence). The student results also provided evidence of a DFC model by showing an interaction between the DFC model and cognitive style (see Table 4), with FD students in the experimental group performing much better than those in the control group (skill: 79.11 vs. 53.73; independence: 99.14 vs. 79.82), suggesting that the DFC model directly ameliorates the steep reliance on external structure for FD students. This finding disproves all null hypotheses (H1-H6) and therefore confirms that:

1. Hypothesis 1 : Rejected. Discovery Flipped Classroom learning model assisted by Google Sites affects students’ mathematics problem-solving skills.
2. Hypothesis 2 : Rejected. The Discovery Flipped Classroom learning model assisted by Google Sites affects students’ learning independence.
3. Hypothesis 3 : Rejected. Cognitive style affects students’ mathematical problem-solving skills.
4. Hypothesis 4 : Rejected. Cognitive style influences student learning independence.
5. Hypothesis 5 : Rejected. There is an interaction between the Discovery Flipped Classroom model assisted by Google Sites with cognitive style on students’ mathematics problem-solving skills.
6. Hypothesis 6 : Rejected. There is an interaction between the Discovery Flipped Classroom model assisted by Google Sites with cognitive style on student learning independence.

So, all null hypotheses were rejected in this study, meaning that applying the DFC model and cognitive style contributed significantly to students' mathematical problem-solving skills and learning independence.

Discussion and Findings

This study demonstrates that implementing the Discovery Flipped Classroom (DFC) learning model aided with Google Sites positively increases students' mathematical problem-solving abilities and learning independence. These results are consistent with literature indicating that the DFC model promotes student engagement and learning success (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2018; Lo & Hew, 2017). The DFC model in classrooms allows students to understand course material at their own pace outside the classroom, followed by discussions and problem-solving during class, fostering a more professional learning environment.

The results of the MANOVA analysis found that the DFC model had a significant effect on mathematics problem-solving skills ($F = 170.996$, $p < 0.001$) and learning independence ($F = 91.333$, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, students who learn through the DFC model can better apply mathematical concepts in real situations, and this model aids students in self-regulation and self-evaluation during the learning process. According to (Al-Marroof and Al-Emran, 2018), these findings are supported by the claim that digital platforms such as Google Sites provide more flexibility, which enhances student independence.

The student's cognitive style also had a substantial impact on learning outcomes. Results showed that students with a field-independent (FI) cognitive style performed significantly better than their field-dependent (FD) peers. This aligns with research indicating that FI students can work independently and organize their study time (Tinajero & Páramo, 1998). The interaction results of the DFC model indicated that FD students in the experimental group showed significant improvements in problem-solving ability and independent learning. This suggests that the DFC model may play an important role in reducing FD students' reliance on external structures, which is crucial for effective learning, as noted by (Chen & Macredie, 2002).

Moreover, the findings are consistent with the work of (Cummings et al., 2015; Vishal, 2024), who emphasized that blended learning environments, such as the DFC model, can cater to diverse learning styles and promote active learning. The flexibility of the DFC model allows for personalized learning experiences, which can be particularly beneficial for students with varying cognitive styles. Additionally, integrating technology into learning has enhanced motivation and engagement, improving academic outcomes (Alegre, 2023; Larisang, 2024). Further supporting this, research (Garrison & Vaughan, 2008) highlights that the flipped classroom approach encourages deeper learning by allowing students to engage with content before class, thus maximizing the time spent on higher-order thinking activities during class. This aligns with the findings of this study, where students demonstrated improved problem-solving skills and learning independence.

Additionally, studies (Bergmann & Sams, 2012) have shown that the flipped classroom model can increase student satisfaction and motivation as students feel more in control of their learning process. This is particularly relevant in the DFC model, where using Google Sites facilitates a more interactive and engaging learning environment.

In general, the findings of this study reject all proposed null hypotheses, indicating that the implementation of the DFC model and cognitive style differences significantly affect students'

mathematical problem-solving abilities and learning independence. This has significant implications for educational practice, particularly optimizing learning to be more inclusive and responsive to students' needs.

Conclusion

The results of this study said that the applicability of the Discovery Model of Flipped Classroom learning with the help of Google Sites could significantly improve the patients' mathematical problem-solving abilities and learning independence. Moreover, students' cognitive styles also influenced learning outcomes, as FI students scored higher in comparison. The interaction of the DFC model and cognitive style indicated that this effective model could improve the student's learning outcomes, even for the students with FD cognitive style..

Recommendation

This study implies that teachers and educators should consider applying the DFC model in learning, especially in learning mathematics, citing this study's findings. Furthermore, researchers should consider the variations in students' cognitive styles in developing more inclusive and adaptive learning strategies. We must also continue to investigate the impact of the DFC model in various educational contexts, both in terms of implementation and educational setting, on student learning outcomes.

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